

Synthesis of Possible Analgetic Agents

S. MUKHERJEE* and B. PATHAK**

Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, Calcutta-9

Manuscript received 27 August 1973; accepted 17 June 1974

A few N-alkyl hexahydro indeno(2,1-c) pyridines were prepared to examine their analgetic activity. These compounds were, however, found to possess high local anesthetic activity.

INDENO(2,1-c) pyridine and some of its derivatives were first synthesized by Mills and co-workers¹. Borsche and Hahn² subsequently extended the work. Plati and co-worker³, later, discovered anti-histaminic activity among this class of compounds. Various useful biological activity⁴⁻⁵ such as anti-histaminic, antiadrenaline, antiacetylcholin and local anesthetic action of phenindamin (Thephorin) and its derivatives prompted many workers⁶⁻¹¹ to develop different methods of synthesis of indeno(2,1-c) pyridine derivatives. Indeno(1,2-c) pyridines have been reported in recent years, to possess sedative, neuroleptic, adrenolytic and analgetic properties¹²⁻¹³.

Considering medicinal values of indeno(2,1-c and 1,2-c) pyridines and in continuation of our previous work¹⁴ on synthesis of indeno(1,2-b)pyridines for pharmacological screening, synthesis of indeno(2,1-c)

Pharmacology: Preliminary examinations have shown that these compounds have no significant analgetic activity but they have high local anesthetic property. Details of pharmacology will be published elsewhere.

Experimental

Ethyl-1-acetyl-2-phenyl propane-1,3-dicarboxylate (II):

Sodium (4.6 g; 0.2 mole) was added to acetoacetic ester (117 g; 0.9 mole) and heated to 100° on an oil bath when all the sodium reacted and dissolved. Ethyl cinnamate (106 g; 0.6 mole) was added to the above mass and the mixture was heated on an oil bath at 120° for 8 hrs. The mass after cooling was treated with a little water and dil HCl (3*N*) until it was acidic to congo-red. It was then extracted

pyridine derivatives (I) by a scheme, shown above, has been undertaken.

with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with bicarbonate solution and water respectively and finally dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The residual oil after removal of solvent was distilled in vacuo at 158°-60°/0.6 mm. Yield 54 g (29.4%). (Found: C, 66.4; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 7.2%).

* Department of Chemistry, Surendranath College, Cal-9.

** To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

2-Carboxy-3-methyl-1H-indene-1-acetic acid (III) :

The diester (II; 61.2 g; 0.2 mole) was added small portion at a time to 550 ml conc. H_2SO_4 (96%), cooled to 10°. When the addition was complete the corked flask was kept at 25° for 3½ hrs. with occasional shaking. The colour of the solution became brownish-red. The liquid was then poured on crushed ice when white solid separated out. The acid was purified by subsequent dissolution in sodium carbonate solution and reprecipitation of the same with HCl. Yield 38 g (81.9%), m.p. 214°-16° (crystallised from rectified spirit). (Found : C, 67.0; H, 4.9. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires, C, 67.2; H, 5.2%).

2-Carboxy-3-methyl-1H-indene-1-acetic acid anhydride (IV) :

Dicarboxylic acid (III; 23.2 g; 0.1 mole) was heated with acetic anhydride (25 ml) in boiling water bath when the substance dissolved and formed a clear solution. Heating was continued for one hour more. On cooling to 20° a solid separated out which was filtered. The ppt was then washed with pet-ether and dried. It may be purified by crystallisation from a small quantity of acetic anhydride. Yield 10 g (46.7%); m.p. 137°-40°. (Found : C, 72.7; H, 4.5. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.7%)

2-Alkyl-9-methyl-1,3-dioxo-2,3,4,4a-tetrahydro-1H-indeno(2,1-c)pyridine (V) :

The anhydride (IV; 4.3 g; 0.02 mole) was added to ice cold *n*-alkyl amine (0.06 mole) and refluxed on a water bath for 3-5 hrs. The residue, after removal of excess amine, was distilled from an oil bath at 220°-30° under reduced pressure. The viscous liquid solidified in some cases and the solid was crystallised from alcohol. Physical data have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

No.	R	Compound V		Compound VI	
		m.p. °C/b.p. °C (mm)	Yield %	b.p. °C(mm)	Yield %
1	CH ₃	142-4	33.0	161-2(0.6)	74.2
2	C ₂ H ₅	159-61	41.5	183-7(1.5)	82.3
3	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	173-5(0.4)	49.0	167-9(0.5)	77.8
4	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	203-5(2)	59.5	220-3(2.8)	84.9

2-Alkyl-9-methyl-1,3-dioxo-2,3,4,4a,9,9a-hexahydro-1H-indeno(2,1-c)pyridine (VI) :

Unsaturated imide (V, 0.01 mole), dissolved in 100 ml alcohol, was hydrogenated at 40°-45° under 45 lbs pressure of H₂ in presence of Pd/C. When the hydrogenation was over, the alcoholic solution was filtered out from the catalyst, the alcohol was removed and the residue thus obtained was distilled under reduced pressure. Physical data have been recorded in Table 1.

2-Alkyl-9-methyl-2,3,4,4a,9,9a-hexahydro-1H-indeno(2,1-c)pyridine (I) :

Saturated imide (VI; 0.01 mole) was reduced by LiAlH₄ in dry ether. It was refluxed for 30 hrs. and then decomposed by required amount of water. The base from the ethereal solution was extracted out with dil HCl. The clear acid extract was then basified with NaOH solution and the liberated amine was again extracted out with ether. Ether was removed and the residual oil was distilled. Relevant data are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2.

COMPOUND I

No.	R	b.p. °C(mm) of base	Yield %	m.p. °C (Picrate)
1	CH ₃	105(0.8)	49.8	190-1
2	C ₂ H ₅	118-20(0.8)	37.2	187-89
3	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	131-33(1)	34.9	186-7
4	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	138-40(1)	37.0	Could not be crystal- lised.

Analytical data corresponded with the calculated values for the elements.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India, for some financial assistance to carry out the work.

References

1. W. H. MILLS, W. H. PALMER and M. G. TOMKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2369.
2. W. BORSCHKE and H. HAHN, *Ann.*, 1939, 537, 229.
3. J. T. PLATI and W. WENNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 209; U.S. Pats., 2,470,108; 2,470,109, 1949.
4. G. LEHMANN, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1948, 92, 249.
5. G. LEHMANN, L. O. RANDALL and E. HAGAN, *Arch. intern. Pharmacodynamie*, 1949, 78, 253.
6. H. J. KAHN, V. PETROW, E. L. REWALD and B. STURGEON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2128.
7. H. HERBERT FOX, JULIAN I. LEWIS and WILHELM WENNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1259.
8. B. N. FEITELSON and V. PETROW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3358.
9. J. N. CHATTERJEA and K. PRASAD, *J. Sci. Ind. Research (India)*, 1955, 14B, 383.
10. J. T. PLATI, ARTHUR K. INGBERMAN and W. WENNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 261.
11. J. T. PLATI and W. WENNER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 1130.
12. SANDOZ LTD. *Neth. Appl.* 6,500,312 (Cl.Co7d), July 19, 1965; *Swiss Appl.* Jan. 17, Sept. 18, and Oct. 20, 1964; *Chem. Abs.* 1966, 64, 3501f.
13. ERNST, JUCKER, ANTON, ERNOETHER, and JEAN M. BASTIAN, (Sandoz Ltd.), Fr. 1,529,080 (Cl.CO7d), A61k, 14 Jun. 1968, Swiss Appl. 21 Jun. 1966, 6 Mar. 1967; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, 71, 13029g.
14. S. MUKHERJEE and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 45.